

National Technical University of Athens

**ISSUES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL
EDUCATION BY THE CREATION OF
A PROTOTYPE TEMPORARY
CHILDREN'S COMMUNITY**

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INTRODUCTION

- Xanthopoulos Th., Urban Republic and the Empire of the Market
URL: <http://itia.ntua.gr/en/docinfo/938>
- Tassios T. P., Why do we want to be train our children?
To Vima, September 2, 2007.

INTRODUCTION

Many scientists believe that the evolution of development/consumption as we determine it today in the globalized economy market and the obvious social/environmental problems that appear can be identified/analyzed and faced by means of technological solutions/applications.

INTRODUCTION

They are confident that the future survival of mankind on Earth is possible within a logical contradiction:

To continue the implementation of the current devouring model of capitalist development and yet lie within the constraints of a stable and sustainable equilibrium, "blushingly" avoiding though to determine and quantify the model's limits.

INTRODUCTION

Others argue (Xanthopoulos 2010) that the historical truth and brutal reality of everyday life reveal a decadent image and pessimistic perspective:

"The political and economic life of our societies organized pulsating over time in the chaotic and frightening pattern of aggressive individual and collective aspirations, leaded by an explosive combination of greed and arrogance that unfortunately characterizes the human species, at least since the time when agricultural and livestock goods began to be produced in surplus."

INTRODUCTION

In “mega-cities”
we consume:

- Goods
- Energy

We produce:

- Services
- Wastes

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

To stop this descent (which brakes also the natural circles) a first obvious goal is to educate citizens of the future to build and live with an alternative model of development.

PREPARATING THE ACTION

- To achieve the application of these observations we have to train new people to have universal learning «mathesis universalis», that is, the foundations of the Cartesian system for durable approach towards the problems and their solving.
- The holistic and rational approach (first level) is the best individual defence against the prevailing principles of «homo economicus» (Human of the Market) and the lifestyle offered by the market's empire.

PREPARATING THE ACTION

Therefore, the challenge is to define the essential needs of young people. In this regard, Prof. T. P. Tassios, observes that these are:

- 1. To build their own conscience, and**
- 2. To survive**

- “For the same reasons, therefore, we offer to children and adolescents the two constituents of education, i.e., Cultivation and Training, for the Consciousness and the Stomach, respectively.
- It should be noted that they must meet both the needs of “being” at the same time (Self-assurance and self-preservation).” It is also defined that culture refers both to the ability of evaluation and to the artistic sensibility, while education refers to the knowledge and to the skills (Tassios 1993, Tassios 2007).

PREPARATING THE ACTION

The aim of the lectures is to mature the idea of participation to the "village of the world " a laboratory where, with the assumption that children will go to live in a specific place and time, they will be asked to determine:

- the conditions of their coexistence
 - land use
 - its infrastructure
 - waste management activity
 - and the ecological and economic footprints of their activities
- that is to gain global **environmental consciousness.**

PREPARATING THE ACTION

Political consciousness: It has been shown that democratic deficits have delivered the world to the rule of the world Market and to the environmental problems it creates

Solidarity: The collectivity and the demonstration of the values that protect the interests of the group and the solidarity of community members is a prerequisite for the practical survival of the group.

PREPARATING THE ACTION

Self-sufficiency: Self-sufficiency in a social formation and community has nothing to do with an integrated closed-circuit production scheme. It seeks to prove that this experimental system has the capacity to produce, based on its needs.

PREPARATING THE ACTION

A series of lectures was initially implemented for "... the development of people, instead of the development of useless products... a true democracy that would involve everybody in a decision-making system, another organization of the education, so that citizens are shaped to be able to lead and to obey, according to an Aristotle's quote" (Kastoriadis 2000).

ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS

POLITICAL CONSCIOUSNESS

SELF-SUFFICIENCY & SOLIDARITY

EXPERIMENTAL LABORATORY

THE VILLAGE OF COSMOS

PROTOTYPE-TEMPORARY

KIDS-COMMUNITY

PREPARATING THE ACTION

Lectures:

1. Nature
2. Kosmos
3. Economy or ecology?
4. Food
5. Materials
- 6.
7. Earth building
8. Energy
9. Waste

3. Economy or ecology?

6. 7. Earth building

PREPARATING THE ACTION

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THE FIELD OF ACTION

The area of the action is specified as **a field that will be prepared so that it can cover (basically) the nutritional needs of children** with appropriate (agricultural) actions and the needs for their accommodation with suitable infrastructure to start implementing earth **architecture by building on their own.**

In this field there will be a repository of materials and drinking water.

THE FIELD OF ACTION

The inventory of stocked materials is as follows:

- appropriate timber and construction materials
- farm tools
- cooking utensils, generator, cooking appliances with gas and some fuel
- bikes, selected games and artistic tools (brushes, paper and clay), etc.

In the field there will be:

- • space for the cultivation of agricultural products
- • pets, farm animals, bees etc.

The field is designed to be -as much as possible- a closed and self-managed system because each person develops an environmental conscience when confronted with the waste he or she produces.

THE FIELD OF ACTION

1. MATERIALS

TOOLS-FEUEL

2.

OTHER PRODUCTS

KIDS-COMMUNITY

THE FIELD OF ACTION

- The activities of the children will be defined by the concept that children should be able to live **self-sufficiently** in a place where they have established and are managing themselves. In order to do so they should be able to function in a coordinated way. **As a result, their collective work will produce all the output for their survival.**
- All the adversities and the difficulties that may arise should be made clear to the children that partake in these activities from the very beginning. **Their task would be to evaluate the circumstances and make their conscious choices in relation to their participation in this project.** As this process moves on, the children will decide the context of their activities in the "Village of World"

THE FIELD OF ACTION

- **Architectural Activities**
- **Agricultural/livestock activities**
- **Environmental management:** The objective of this activity is to distinguish the so-called **“entries” and “exits” of the community system.** To fulfil this criterion, waste will be stored in a close distance to where children live, as a reminder for them to take appropriate waste management decisions. Furthermore, energy consumption, which will come from various resources, will be determined from the very beginning of the project. Finally, any other needs that may arise and can only be satisfied by the wider market will be assessed and evaluated by all children to investigate their characteristics.
- **Games and Entertainment:** The games will be utterly different and distinct from all the games of an urban lifestyle

CONCLUSIONS

- The aim of this social experiment is to achieve the organisation, the order and the perception of community of the children through **the creation of a collective vision** (production of the collective work of survival), which is generally conflicting with the more established “values of the individual”.

- This will definitely **depend on the preparation of the children, on their experiences, on how well they will perceive** the new reality that they will face and on whether they will be able to coexist with different individuals in a realistic, therefore harsh natural environment.
- Under these circumstances they will be **required to demonstrate emotional maturity, to develop policy perception, to exercise manual work** and other features.

CONCLUSIONS

Nevertheless, it is a fact that the consuming society of the Market has “trained” children in a profound and universal prevalence of greed, arrogance, egoism and cynicism.

This project will attempt to function under a completely different mindset, where is very difficult to predict in what manner and to what extent it will affect the children.

This project however may trigger thoughts (maybe a new beginning) for them to consider and discuss.

CONCLUSIONS

So, waiting the awakening of the critical mass that will spawn the "event of the history" for the reversal of this suicidal path from the dead-end under the domination of the Empire of the Market, it is hoped that the proposed project, which has already be given positive samples during the second phase of preparation, may awake old memories (today forgotten) of ecologically balanced models and sustainable societies.

In any case, the application of the project will lead to a self-improvement function in order to discharge from practical and theoretical errors and utopias, a necessary step to improve the application of its foundation.

Project URL

ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS
POLITICAL CONSCIOUSNESS
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